

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

Coordinator Approval Cover Sheet

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D2.9

CFD simulations of noise from subcomponents

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X-ROTOR Consortium

University of Strathclyde

Delft University of Technology

University College Cork – National University of Ireland, Cork

Fundacion Cener

General Electric Renovables España

Norwegian University of Science and Technology

CENER

NTNU – Trondheim
Norwegian University of
Science and Technology

UCC
Coláiste na hOllscoile Corcaigh, Éire
University College Cork, Ireland

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This report is part of deliverable D2.9, titled "3D CFD simulations of noise from a full X-Rotor concept." High fidelity numerical computational fluid dynamic (CFD) simulations have been carried out using the lattice-Boltzmann very large eddy simulation (LB-VLES) solver 3DS PowerFLOW. The assessment initially focused on the aerodynamic performance and flow field surrounding the X-Rotor baseline concept. Subsequently, the aeroacoustics performance at various observer locations was determined by using the solid formulation of the Ffowcs Williams & Hawkings (FW-H) acoustic analogy. Results suggest that the low-frequency noise emitted by the X-Rotor is primarily dominated by tonal noise originating from interactions between the lower blades and the secondary rotor. In contrast, the high-frequency noise is predominantly attributed to the broadband noise generated by the secondary rotors.

List of acronyms

BPF	Blade passing frequency
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
FH-W	Ffowcs-Williams & Hawkings
GCI	Grid convergence index
LBM	Lattice-Boltzmann method
LRF	Local reference frame
OSPL	Overall sound pressure level
SPL	Sound pressure level
SWL	Sound power level
TSR	Tip speed ratio
VAWT	Vertical axis wind turbine
VLES	Very large eddy simulation
VR	Variable resolution

1 Introduction

The report is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a detailed description of the simulation setup, incorporating slight modifications compared to those presented in the previous report (Milestone 2.3, submitted on December 20th, 2022). These adjustments were implemented in response to artificial problems found in the previous setup that significantly impacted acoustic results. The simulation result is presented in section 3. The last section summarizes the conclusions of the work.

2 Simulation setup

2.1 Wind turbine Geometry

The blade profiles used in this simulation were consistent with the previous report. The upper and lower blades of the primary rotor are 100 m and 65 m long, respectively, with coning angles of 30° and 50° . The airfoil profiles are the NACA 0025 and NACA 0008, respectively. The chord is linearly reduced from the blade root to the tip for both the upper and lower blades. Specifically, the upper blade chord, $c_p^{(u)}$, decreases from 10 m to 5 m, while the lower blade chord, $c_p^{(l)}$, decreases from 14 m to 7 m. No twist and pitch angles are applied along the radial direction of the primary rotor blades. For the secondary rotor, the airfoil profile FFA-W3-241 is used for the entire blade, the twist angle and the chord length, c_s , distributions are shown in Figure 1. The primary rotor has a radius $R_t^{(p)} = 75$ m, and the secondary rotor has a radius $R_t^{(s)} = 4.69$ m. Two secondary rotors, each connected to a cylinder-shaped generator, are fixed to the tips of the lower blades, as illustrated in Figure 2. Moreover, the distance between the secondary rotor tip and the leading edge of the lower blade is 1.56 m.

Figure 1. Secondary rotor blade profile

There are 3 local reference frame (LRF) coordinate systems set for the simulation of the X-Rotor baseline concept, as is shown in Figure 2. The primary rotor rotates around the x_p – axis at a fixed speed $\Omega_p = 0.833$ rad/s, resulting in a tip Mach number of 0.19. The rotational centre O_p is 100 m above sea level. The secondary rotors are located at the lower blade tips and rotate around the x_{s_1} and x_{s_2} – axis, respectively, at a constant speed of $\Omega_s = 43.06$ rad/s, resulting in a tip Mach number of 0.59. The incoming freestream velocity is set at $V_\infty = 12.5$ m/s towards the positive z - direction in the global coordinate system.

Figure 2. The local reference frame coordinate systems for the X-Rotor baseline concept geometry and the dimensions.

2.2 Simulation domain setup

The simulation domain is a rectangular box, as presented in Figure 3. The origin of the primary rotor coordinate system O_p is placed $18.5R_t^{(p)}$ downstream of the inlet and $37R_t^{(p)}$ away from other sides. To minimize the influence of vortex shedding from the tower base on the wind turbine's flow field, the distance from the tower base to the X-Rotor rotational centre O_p is set to $11.437R_t^{(p)}$. In addition to this, two spherical-shaped acoustic sponge regions are implemented at a distance $4.7R_t^{(p)}$ and $12.45R_t^{(p)}$ from O_p are employed. These regions are utilized to minimize the backward reflection of the acoustic waves from the outer boundary. This approach is accomplished by exponentially increasing the value of fluid kinematic viscosity from its physical value within the inner sphere, gradually up to an artificial value of two orders of magnitude higher beyond the outer sphere. At the inlet, the freestream velocity V_∞ , the turbulent intensity $I = 10.2\%$ and turbulent length scale $L = 145$ m are set as boundary conditions. The turbulent intensity and turbulent length scale are evaluated using the method described by Zhu et al. (Zhu et al., 2005). At the outlet, ambient pressure $p_\infty = 1.00125 \times 10^5$ Pa is set for a pressure boundary condition. For other walls at the edge, the slip wall boundary conditions are applied.

Figure 3. Side view of the simulation domain.

The computational domain is discretised in 15 different variable resolution (VR) regions, ranging from the coarse resolution VR0 to the finest resolution VR14, with the grid resolution varying by a factor of 2 between adjacent VR regions as shown in Figure 4. For current study, due to the higher computational cost and substantial storage space requirement, the finest voxel $\delta x = 9.525 \times 10^{-3}$ m is employed, equivalent to a resolution of 50 voxels along the mean chord, c_{s_s} , at the secondary rotor blade as presented in Table 1, which results an average $y^+ = 1000$ on the secondary rotor blade surface with total 23.5 million fine equivalent voxels for the entire simulation domain. Furthermore, the physical time step, corresponding to a Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number of 1 in the finest voxel resolution is 6.43874×10^{-6} second. The computational cost is about 4.88×10^4 CPU hours/rev on a 480 cores cluster (Linux Xeon® Gold 6148 2.4GHz Platform).

Figure 4. Sketch of computational setup and VR regions distributions.

Type	Resolution $c_s/\delta x$, y^+	Fine equivalent voxels	CPU hours per revolution
Coarse	25, $y^+ = 2000$	8.2 million	9.57×10^3
Medium	35, $y^+ = 1410$	14.5 million	2.33×10^4
Fine	50, $y^+ = 1000$	23.5 million	4.88×10^4

Table 1. Voxel size and physical time step with resolution.

The entire fluid domain for both medium and fine grid resolution simulations is initialized with converged results obtained from the instantaneous flow field of the coarse grid resolution simulation. As presented in Figure 5, it is evident that from the coarse grid resolution result, the average tangential force for each rotation stabilizes for both the primary rotor and the secondary rotors after the 7th rotation. The flow data is sampled throughout one complete revolution of the primary rotor, starting from the 8th revolution. Meanwhile, the unsteady pressure on the solid surface of the X-Rotor, utilized for predicting far-field acoustics at the corresponding locations, is sampled over a period of two revolutions starting from the 7th revolution. Where, the far-field acoustic pressure is predicted through the Ffowcs Williams & Hawkings' (FW-H) acoustic analogy (Ffowcs Williams & Hawkings, 1969), with formulation 1 A developed by (Farassat & Succi, 1980) is employed as a solution of FW-H equation and solved in a forward-time (Casalino, 2003) by integrating the unsteady pressure on the solid surfaces on the X-Rotor. The approach is carried out using two post-processing software, one is SIMULIA PowerACOUSTICS® for evaluation the noise emitted from the primary rotor, while the secondary rotors are predicted using Opty∂B® -PFNOISESCANE developed by Casalino (Casalino et al., 2021). The acoustic pressure from the primary and the secondary rotors is then superimposed at the observer locations. In the fine resolution simulation, the sampling frequency is set at 24.5 kHz, accompanied by an averaging spatial resolution of 0.019 m on the solid FW-H integration surface, reaching the upper temporal and spatial limits of the corresponding VR resolution, resulting in the generation of a 5 TB solid FW-H surface results dataset.

Figure 5. Time average tangential force of the primary rotor and the combined forces of the two secondary rotors, computed over each rotation of the primary rotor.

2.3 Noise measurement setup

A recall of the observe positions and the coordinate system is shown in Figure 6, the far-field acoustic pressure is measured in both polar direction ($x - z$ plane) and azimuthal direction ($y - z$ plane), with each direction using 8 virtual microphones. The measurements are performed at two distances with the microphones located 200 m ($2.6 R_t^{(p)}$) and 400 ($5.3 R_t^{(p)}$) from the rotational centre O_p .

Figure 6 15 microphones are placed at (a) polar angles of X-Rotor in $x - z$ plane, and (b) azimuthal angles of X-Rotor in $y - z$ plane respectively with a distance of 200 m ($2.6 R_t^{(p)}$) from O_p

3 Simulation results

3.1 Grid independence study

In this section, a grid independent study is performed to analyse the sensitivity of the numerical solution to the three different grid resolutions: coarse, medium and fine with a refinement ratio of $M = \sqrt{2}$, as shown in Table 1. Also, to evaluate the rotor performance conveniently, the following non-dimensional parameters are introduced.

The pressure coefficient, C_p , defined as

$$C_p = \frac{p - p_\infty}{0.5 \rho_0 V_\infty^2}, \quad (1)$$

The power coefficient, C_p , defined as

$$C_p = \frac{P}{0.5 \rho_0 A_{rot} V_\infty^3}. \quad (2)$$

where ρ_0 is the air density, A_{rot} is the swept area of the rotor, p is the static pressure and P the power.

Figure 7 presents the phase averaged aerodynamic results obtained from coarse, medium and fine mesh resolutions for both the primary rotor and the secondary rotor against the primary rotor azimuthal angle ϕ_p . Overall, the curves exhibit comparable shapes and values thus demonstrating a converging trend.

Figure 7. Phase averaged results obtained from coarse, medium and fine resolutions against the primary rotor azimuthal positions ϕ_p . Subplot (a) represents the power coefficient of the primary rotor and subplot (b) presents the thrust of the secondary rotor.

Figure 8 shows the variation of the time average primary rotor C_p and the secondary rotor thrust with the number of grid points for each grid resolution setting. Each data point corresponds to a normalized grid spacing, normalized by the length of the finest grid, ranging from 2 (coarse) to 1 (fine). The value of 0 represents a hypothetical converged result obtained by Richardson extrapolation. Convergence is assessed using the value of grid convergence index (GCI) (Roache, 1998), as defined in eq. (3). For subplot (a) $GCI_{1,1.4} = 10.19\%$, $GCI_{1.4,2} = 22.07\%$ for C_p of the primary rotor with GCI ratio equals to 1.087, which is approximately equal to 1, indicating solutions within the asymptotic range of convergence. The extrapolation value of $C_p = 0.39$ represented as a red empty square is calculated using the refinement ratio $M = \sqrt{2}$ and the order of convergence $N = 2$ (Roache, 1997), aligning well with the designed value 0.39 to 0.4 obtained from QBLADE software. Similarly, for the subplot (b) $GCI_{1,1.4} = 3.37\%$, $GCI_{1.4,2} = 8.67\%$ for the average thrust of the secondary rotor and the GCI ratio equals to 1.0413, that also close to 1. The extrapolated averaged thrust value of 4.74×10^4 N indicates an 11.5% under prediction compared to the results obtained by CENER using OpenFOAM with the k-omega-SST model. This deviation can be attributed to the difference of simulation conditions. CENER's results involve a stationary simulation where only an isolated secondary rotor rotates around its own horizontal axis with an inflow speed equivalent to the primary rotor's lower blade tip speed. This setup excludes some important factors that can affect the aerodynamic performance. These include the rapid changes of the inflow speed caused by the secondary rotor rotating around the

vertical axis of the primary rotor, the interactions between the secondary rotor and the lower blade, and the complex wake interactions with the secondary rotor.

$$GCI = \frac{GCI_{1.4,2}}{M^N GCI_{1,1.4}} \quad (3)$$

Figure 8. Trend of the time average (a) the primary rotor C_p , and (b) the secondary rotor thrust with the number of grid points for each resolution setting. The number of each data point corresponds to the normalized grid spacing, which is normalized by the length of the finest grid, starting from grid spacing 2 (coarse) to 1 (fine), where spacing 0 indicates a hypothetical converged result evaluated by the Richardson extrapolation.

Figure 9 illustrates the acoustic results obtained from the coarse, medium and fine grid resolutions at an observer distance of 400 m from the primary rotor rotational centre O_p . The subplots (a) and (b) show the overall sound pressure level (OSPL) at different polar angles ϕ_p , and azimuthal angles ϕ_p , respectively. Similar to the aerodynamic results, the results exhibit a converging trend. Furthermore, the directivity of the OSPL results show little dependence on the different observer locations, particularly at the azimuthal locations with a maximum difference about 1.7 dB between the lowest value of 72.9 dB ($\phi_p = 135^\circ$) and the highest value 74.6 dB ($\phi_p = 225^\circ$). Additionally, the averaged OSPL for observer distances of 200 m and 400 m in polar directions are 81.5 dB and 75.6 dB, respectively, and in azimuthal directions are 79.9 dB and 73.7 dB, respectively. These results align with the inverse squared law, indicating a 6 dB decay for the OSPL as the observer distance doubles. Leveraging this relationship allows for a rapid evaluation of the noise level at further observer distances. Furthermore, applying an A-weighting filter to convert the noise level to reflect

human ear sensitivity across the spectrum. The A-weighted OSPL for a distance of 400 m is 63.5 dBA, approximately equivalent to the sound level produced in a busy general office environment.

Subplot (c) illustrates the sound pressure level (SPL) spectra observed at the upwind most location $\phi_p = 180^\circ$. The SPL values from the three different grid resolutions at the frequency of the first BPF harmonics of the secondary rotor are almost identical to each other. Furthermore, the broadband noise levels between the medium and fine grid resolutions are similar below 300 Hz, while the results for the simulation with coarse grid resolution are underpredicted. Additionally, a frequency shift is evident in the broadband noise when comparing results across coarse to medium and medium to fine grid resolutions, accompanied by notable underpredictions of noise levels for frequencies larger than 1000 Hz. This is due to the inadequate grid resolution, which does not sufficiently resolve the smaller turbulent structures near the FW-H solid surface, resulting in inaccurate predictions of the broadband noise level, similar results were also observed by (Lockard et al., 2014)

Figure 9. Plots of the acoustic results obtained from the coarse, medium and fine grid resolutions at an observer distance 400 m from the primary rotor rotational centre O_p . Subplots (a) and (b) represent the OSPL against the different polar angles θ_p and azimuthal angles ϕ_p , respectively. Subplot (c) is the SPL spectra observed at the upwind most location for $\phi_p = 270^\circ$.

3.2 Aerodynamic and flow field results discussion

The flow data from the fine grid resolution simulation (for the sake of brevity, the fine simulation results will not be mentioned hereafter) was post-processed using the post-processing tool SIMULIA PowerVIZ® and Figure 10 shows the instantaneous turbulent flow structures generated by the X-Rotor using the iso-surface of the λ_2 -criterion. The colour contours represent the non-dimensional velocity magnitude V_{mag}/V_∞ . The flow features are clearly revealed, particularly the interactions between the secondary rotor slipstream and the lower blade. The observed faster downstream expansion of the secondary rotor slipstream generated from the tip and root region at $\phi_p = 180^\circ$ can be attributed to the aligned direction of freestream velocity and relative inflow velocity to the secondary rotor plane. In contrast, at $\phi_p = 0^\circ$, where these velocities oppose each other, a relatively slower downstream flow is evident. Furthermore, the impact of wake interactions at $\phi_p = 180^\circ$ (as discussed previously), manifests in the distortion of the slipstream close to the inner side of the lower blade's trailing edge region. Additionally, vortex shedding from the root of the upper blade is evident at $\phi_p = 0^\circ$ that are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 10. Instantaneous turbulence structure visualization using iso-surface of λ_2 -criterion for vortex identification ($\lambda_2 = -300 \text{ s}^{-1}$) colour contoured with the dimensionless velocity magnitude V_{mag}/V_∞ .

As the results presented in Figure 7, subplot (a) reveals a decrease of the primary rotor C_p at about $\phi_p = 90^\circ$ and 270° is due to the lower blades and the tower wake interactions at the downwind locations. While in subplot (b), the small fluctuations of the secondary rotor thrust can be attributed to the interaction between the secondary rotor and the wake generated by another secondary rotor, by its own wake and the wake from the tower, details are presented in Figure 11.

Figure 11 below illustrates the instantaneous flow field around the X-Rotor at the plane of the rotational centre of the secondary rotor. It presents the non-dimensional vorticity magnitude $\omega c_s/V_\infty$ at different azimuthal positions, ϕ_p . Notably, rotor-wake interactions are predominantly observed in the downwind section of the X-Rotor. For instance, it can be observed that the interactions between the rotor and the wake generated from the other secondary rotor occur at the azimuthal positions $\phi_p = 15^\circ, 125^\circ$ and 180° , as shown in subplot (a), (c) and (e) respectively. Also, the interactions of the secondary rotor with its own wake occur at about $\phi_p = 155^\circ$, can be observed. Additionally, the vortex ring produced by the secondary rotor and the generator in the upwind region travels in the freestream direction, interacting with the tower and causing the shedding of a Kármán vortex street from the tower. This vortex street subsequently impinges on the secondary rotor at $\phi_p = 90^\circ$. These interactions further explain the thrust fluctuations at the corresponding positions as shown above.

Figure 11. The instantaneous flow field is visualized through the non-dimensional vorticity magnitude $\omega c_s/V_\infty$. Sub-figures (a-e) depict the flow field for the X-Rotor at various azimuthal positions ϕ_p at the plane of the centre of the secondary rotor.

Similarly, in Figure 12, the instantaneous non-dimensional x-vorticity $\omega_x c_s/V_\infty$ is shown at two different planes. Subplots (a-c) and (d-f) correspond to the position at $10\% R_t^{(p)}$ of the upper and lower blades at various azimuthal positions, respectively. The wake interactions for both upper and lower blades are clearly demonstrated. As shown in subplot (a, d) at azimuthal positions $\phi_p = 90^\circ, 270^\circ$ the flow is attached on the surface of the blade for both upper and lower blade. As the primary rotor continues to rotate, particularly when the blade reaches the downstream position around azimuthal angle $\phi_p = 330^\circ$, flow separations

become apparent at approximately the mid-chord position on the inner surface of the upper blade. This is characterized by opposing x-vorticities. Conversely, the flow remains attached to both surfaces of the lower blade during this phase. When the azimuthal angle increases to $\phi_p = 0^\circ$, the flow separations on the upper blade become more pronounced. The positive vortex from the leading edge interacts with the negative vortex close to the trailing edge and shedding off and forming a vortex pair in the near-wake region. In contrast, small disturbances can be observed on the inner surface of the lower blade.

Figure 12. The instantaneous flow field is visualized through the non-dimensional x-vorticity $\omega_x c_s / V_\infty$. Sub-figures (a-c) and (d-f) present the flow field for the X-Rotor at various azimuthal positions ϕ_p at the planes of the 10% $R_t^{(p)}$ of the upper blade and lower blade, respectively. Contours (a, d), (b, e) and (c, f) have been extracted at the same time instance.

The instantaneous standard deviation pressure coefficient, $C_{P_{std}}$, on the lower blade tip region at the azimuthal angle around $\phi_p = 0^\circ$ is presented in Figure 13. Subplots (a) to (c) present three offset positions during the passage of the reference blade to the lower blade leading edge, corresponding to the offset angles at $\phi_{offset}^{(s)} = -36^\circ, 0^\circ$ and 36° . The footprint of the secondary rotor tip vortex on the surface inside and outside the lower blade tip region is demonstrated clearly. In Addition to this, due to the direct impingement of the tip vortices, the inside part exhibits a higher pressure than those observed on the outside part of the lower blade. Moreover, an increasing of the $C_{P_{std}}$ close to the leading edge of the lower blade tip region can be observed during the passage of the reference blade, which is likely due to the effect of the potential field interactions.

Figure 13. Instantaneous standard deviation pressure coefficient, $C_{p_{std}}$, on the lower blade tip at azimuthal angle around $\phi_p = 0^\circ$. Subplots (a) to (c) present three offset positions during the passage of the reference blade to the lower blade leading edge, corresponding to the offset angles at $\phi_{offset}^{(s)} = -36^\circ, 0^\circ$ and 36° .

Figure 14 presents the power spectral density (PSD) of the lower blade forces F_x, F_y and F_z in three directions. Noticeable spikes appear at various integer multiples of the secondary rotor blade passing frequency. Particularly in the axial direction force F_x , up to 4 BPF are distinctly observed, while the other two

direction forces exhibit peaks only up to 2 BPF. These patterns can be attributed to the interactions between the secondary rotor and the tip of the lower blade as discussed above, and may result in low-frequency tonal noise in the far field (Yauwenas et al., 2021; Zajamsek et al., 2019).

Figure 14. Plots of the PSD of the lower blade force in three directions.

3.3 Aeroacoustics results

Figure 15 plots the contributions to OSPL from different subcomponents of the X-Rotor based on the fine simulation results at a 400 m distance from the primary rotor rotational centre O_p , at different observer locations. The OSPL is expressed in dB with reference pressure $p_{ref} = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ Pa, and the results are integrated from 20 Hz to 5000 Hz. In general, the OSPL generated by the lower blades and secondary rotors are at similar levels and contribute significantly to the total noise emitted by the X-Rotor. Additionally, the generators also make notable contributions at specific observer locations, such as the upwind most ($\phi_p = 270^\circ$) and downwind most ($\phi_p = 90^\circ$) locations. Conversely, the contribution of the upper blades to the total noise can be neglected, with an average of 15 dB less than those generated by the secondary rotor and the lower blades.

Figure 15. Plots of the contributions to OSPL from different components from fine simulation results at a 400 m distance from the primary rotor rotational centre O_p . For (a) in polar direction and (b) in the azimuthal direction.

To evaluate the contribution of each subcomponent to the overall noise level, SPL spectra at various polar and azimuthal angles are depicted in Figure 16 and Figure 17 respectively. The data are processed using MATLAB pwelch function to estimate the PSD with a Hanning window of 50% overlap and bandwidth of 3.42 Hz (equivalent to one-tenth of the secondary rotor BPF). The results suggest that the secondary rotors are the primary sources of noise for the X-Rotor, dominating the noise spectra across the entire frequency range, particularly at high frequencies, at most observer locations. Additionally, due to the interactions between the lower blades and the secondary rotors, the lower blades significantly contribute to the noise level in the low-frequency region, especially for the tones corresponding to the first few BPF harmonics of the secondary rotor. These results agree well with the force PSD spectra presented in Figure 14. Furthermore, the contribution of broadband noise from the lower and upper blades can be neglected compared to those generated by the secondary rotors and the generators across all observer locations. Moreover, the findings suggest that the generator could potentially be a significant noise source, exhibiting a pronounced directivity pattern in broadband noise. This contributes significantly to the noise at frequencies below 200 Hz or above 2000 Hz at various observer locations. It's worth noting that in the current simulation, the generator is modelled as a simple 2 m diameter cylinder, which could be further optimized in the future to mitigate noise levels.

Figure 16. Comparison of SPL spectra produced by different blades at different polar angles. For (a) $\theta_p = 0^\circ$, (b) $\theta_p = 90^\circ$, (c) $\theta_p = 180^\circ$, (d) $\theta_p = 225^\circ$.

Figure 17. Comparison of sound pressure level spectra (20 Hz bandwidth) produced by different blades at different azimuthal angles. For (a) $\phi_p = 0^\circ$, (b) $\phi_p = 45^\circ$, (c) $\phi_p = 135^\circ$, (d) $\phi_p = 225^\circ$.

The results above offer a broad overview of the noise level contributions from various subcomponents of the X-Rotor. To further visualize the distribution of noise sources across each subcomponent, a band-pass filter is applied to calculate the power spectrum pressure (PSP) on the solid FW-H surfaces of the X-Rotor. The calculation is performed by averaging the unsteady pressure on these surfaces over one entire rotation. This is presented in Figure 18 with six different frequency regions are presented: 25 — 75 Hz, 75 — 125 Hz, 150 — 250 Hz, 500 — 1500 Hz, 1500 — 2500 Hz and 2500 — 3500 Hz at various frequencies, denoted as f_c . The results clearly illustrate the distribution of noise sources on the X-Rotor, characterized by higher PSP values at specific portions of the rotors.

It's clear that the secondary rotor is the main source of noise across all frequencies, as presented in subplots (a-f), compared to other parts. Especially in the lower frequency range (for f_c up to 200 Hz), high PSP values spread throughout the entire secondary rotor. As frequency increases, these high PSP values become more prominent on both sides of the secondary rotor blade tip region and at the root region near the trailing edge on the suction side. This is attributed to the higher velocities experienced by the blade tip region, while the vortices are shed close to the root region of the blade, as illustrated in Figure 10. Moreover, the region with relatively higher PSP values at the blade leading edge decreases gradually from the blade root to tip as frequency increases. This could be due to either variations in local wind speeds experienced along the radial direction of the blades or the influence of blade tip vortex interactions.

For the lower blade, due to its interaction with the secondary rotor, the figures presented below exhibit expected features, for which the higher PSP values can be observed at the blade tip region, particularly close to the blade leading edge for the f_c smaller than 500 Hz. Notably, the direct impingement of the secondary rotor tip vortex on the inside of the lower blade region results in a broader region of PSP values compared to the blade's outside region. Additionally, there is a relatively weaker contribution from the inner part of the upper blade root region, which can be attributed to vortex shedding resulting from flow separation as explained in the previous section.

Regarding the lower blade, its interaction with the secondary rotor leads to anticipated features observed in the presented figures. Specifically, higher PSP values are noticeable at the blade tip region, particularly near the leading edge, for frequencies smaller than 500 Hz. Notably, the direct impingement of the secondary rotor tip vortex on the inside of the lower blade results in a broader distribution of PSP values compared to the outside part of the blade. Additionally, there is a relatively weaker contribution from the inside of the upper blade root region, attributed to vortex shedding resulting from flow separation, as shown above.

Figure 18. Contours of averaged the power spectrum pressure on the solid FW-H surfaces of the X-Rotor for different bandwidths centered at frequencies (a) $f_c = 50$ Hz, (b) $f_c = 100$ Hz, (c) $f_c = 200$ Hz, (d) $f_c = 1000$ Hz, (e) $f_c = 2000$ Hz, and (f) $f_c = 3000$ Hz. The results are averaged over one entire rotation of the primary rotor.

Figure 19 (a, b) displays the results of the time-frequency analysis for the acoustic pressure generated by the secondary rotor and the corresponding acoustic pressure at the observer location $\theta_p = 90^\circ$, which is

positioned 400 m directly above the X-Rotor centre O_p . To explore the relationship between the movement of the secondary rotor and the noise signal at the receiver location, we synchronized the acoustic pressure measurements at the microphone location with the azimuthal positions of sound emission by the rotor. The acoustic pressure was processed for PSD calculated using a Hanning window with a bandwidth of 6.85 Hz equivalent to 1/5 BPF of the secondary rotor and 75% overlap. A small acoustic pressure fluctuation for the rotor at around $\phi_p = 15^\circ$, resulting in fluctuations of SPL values at the BPF harmonics. This phenomenon arises due to wake interactions from the other secondary rotor, as illustrated in Figure 11. As the secondary rotor moves from the downwind position to the upwind location particularly from $\phi_p = 90^\circ$ to $\phi_p = 270^\circ$, the SPL at the fundamental BPF harmonics increases, corresponding to the steady loading on the secondary rotor. This increase follows an upward trend, reaching its peak at approximately $\phi_p = 180^\circ$, as observed in Figure 7. During this stage, the increase in broadband noise level is clearly demonstrated.

Figure 19. (a) plots of the time – frequency analysis for the acoustic pressure observed at a distance 400 m directly above the X-Rotor at $\theta_p = 90^\circ$, (b) corresponds to the time history acoustic pressure. All the time scale is converted to the emission time and normalized to rotor azimuthal positions.

To provide a clear comparison of the noise levels produced by the X-Rotor, the A-weighted sound power level (SWL) from the X-Rotor, calculated by averaging the results in azimuthal and polar directions, is utilized and contrasted with other conventional wind turbines. However, as there is a lack of online acoustic measurement data available for offshore wind turbines, the acoustic results for onshore horizontal wind turbines measured by Moller and Pedersen (Møller & Pedersen, 2011) are utilized as a standard for comparison. The A-weighted SWL presented in Figure 20 in one-third octave bands for wind turbines around

2.5, 5, and 10 MW is estimated from measurement results obtained from 48 large and small wind turbines. It is evident that the SWL from the X-Rotor is significantly higher than that from the other three types of wind turbines, particularly in the higher frequency region, with a maximum of 20 dBA, 23 dBA and 26 dBA difference above 2000 Hz. This higher noise level is primarily attributed to the secondary rotors as discussed above.

Figure 20. Comparison of the A-weighted sound power level (SWL) in one-third octave bands between the X-Rotor and 2.5, 5, and 10 MW wind turbines.

4 Conclusion and future work

This report presents the results obtained from high-fidelity numerical simulations of the baseline concept for the X-Rotor operating at maximum power extraction condition. The approach uses a high-fidelity CFD simulation based on the LBM/VLES method, and the far-field acoustics are computed using the solid FW-H approach. The results give an overview of the aerodynamic and aeroacoustics performance.

The aerodynamic analysis involves comparing the time-averaged primary rotor C_p and the secondary rotor thrust with coarse, medium and fine grid resolutions. Convergence trends are assessed via the GCI values, with the GCI ratio indicating convergence within the asymptotic range. The extrapolated primary rotor C_p value aligns closely with the expected value from QBLADE software, however the secondary rotor thrust results exhibit a 12% deviation compared to the OpenFOAM results with the secondary rotor operated under a stationary condition, nevertheless, the results are in reasonable agreement. The analysis of the flow field around the X-Rotor reveals predominant rotor-wake interactions, particularly in the downwind section. Interactions between tower and rotor wakes, including those from other secondary rotors, are observed at specific azimuthal positions. These findings emphasize the complex dynamics of rotor-wake interactions in X-Rotor configurations.

The OSPL results indicate minimal directivity variation in the noise generated by the X-Rotor across observer locations, with only a 1.7 dB difference between the lowest and highest values. Additionally, secondary rotors significantly contribute to the overall noise level, especially in higher frequency regions. Interaction with the secondary rotor amplifies tonal noise at the first several BPF harmonics from the lower blade tip region. Moreover, the generator has the potential to produce substantial broadband noise, particularly between 100 Hz and 200 Hz or above 1000 Hz at specific observer locations. Furthermore, noise from the upper blades is comparatively negligible compared to contributions from other X-Rotor subcomponents. By utilizing a band-pass filter, the PSP values on the X-Rotor's solid FW-H surfaces are calculated, revealing the distribution of

the noise source across different frequency ranges. The results once again confirm that the secondary rotor is the primary noise source, with substantial contributions from the rotor blade root, tip, and leading edge regions as frequency increases. Furthermore, for the lower blade, interactions with the secondary rotor led to higher PSP values near the blade tip region, particularly close to the leading edge.

Finally, a comparison of A-weighted one-third octave band SWL between the X-Rotor and three different conventional horizontal wind turbines, each with power ratings at 2.5, 5, and 10 MW, is performed. The results indicate that due to the secondary rotor's higher tip speed, the noise level is significantly higher, exceeding that of other turbines by over 20 dB above 2000 Hz under maximum power extraction conditions. The considerably high noise level generated by the current baseline concept of X-Rotor suggests the need to optimize the current design to mitigate noise in the future, particularly by reducing the noise from the secondary rotor.

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